

An empirical subleading correction to Wolf's formula for consecutive prime gaps

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Abstract

Wolf's 1998 conjecture gives $N_g(N) \sim C_g \cdot \text{Li}_2(N) \cdot \exp(-gC_g/\ln N)$ for the count of consecutive prime gaps of size g up to N . (We adopt the variant with C_g in the suppression exponent; the original preprint has $\exp(-g/\ln N)$, see Sec. 1.) On a dataset of $n = 140$ points covering $N \in [10^5, 10^{13}]$, the residual $R(g, N) := \log(N_g^{\text{emp}}(N)/W(g, N))$ is captured by a two-parameter linear model without intercept of the form

$$R(g, N) \approx a \phi(\omega(g)) - b \log \log N,$$

where $\omega(g)$ is the number of distinct prime divisors of g and ϕ is any strictly monotonic transform. On the primary-filtered support $\omega(g) \in \{1, 2\}$, so $\phi \in \{\sqrt{\omega}, \omega, \log \omega, \omega - 1, \sqrt{\omega - 1}\}$ give identical fits (see §3.3); the relevant arithmetic feature is $\omega(g)$, the functional form is not pinned down by the data. For a numerical quote we take the linear representative, $a = 0.349$, $b = 0.202$, on the heuristic of §4.1; the relaxed-filter ranking ($\omega \succ \sqrt{\omega}$ at $\rho_{\max} = 4$) lies outside Wolf's regime of validity (loss $L \approx 87$ vs. 1.11) and is not evidence about the correction inside it. The originally fitted square-root form gives $a = 0.855$, $b = 0.202$. The coefficients depend on the filter: tightening to $\rho \in [0.33, 0.95]$ shrinks $|a|$ and $|b|$ by about 20% (Tab. 3). We have no theoretical derivation for either value. A likelihood-ratio test does not require a free intercept ($p = 0.19$); BIC prefers the no-intercept form. Hold-out-one- N cross-validation gives median $R_{\text{CV}}^2 = 0.92$ (range $[0.69, 0.94]$), with a plateau at $R^2 \approx 0.94$ for $N \gtrsim 10^9$ and $R^2 = 0.874$ at the largest held-out value $N = 10^{13}$. Features that break the two-value bijection ($\log C_g, \sigma_0(g)$) are rejected by $\Delta\text{AIC} \geq 47$. Under a relaxed filter ($\rho_{\max} = 4$, $n = 553$, outside Wolf's regime of validity) linear ω is preferred over $\sqrt{\omega}$ by $\Delta\text{AIC} \approx 10$, in line with the heuristic of §4.1. A five-parameter model that jointly reparametrises the Wolf exponent fits better (nominal $\Delta\text{AIC} = -110.8$; rescaled to $n_{\text{eff}} \approx 25$, $\Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{eff}} \approx -19.8$). Because the histograms are not independent, the nominal $n = 140$ values overstate evidence; we report the rescaled values alongside. The two-parameter form is the minimally parametrised descriptor, not the best fit.

1 Introduction

The distribution of primes is one of the oldest open problems in mathematics. Although the Prime Number Theorem gives $\pi(N) \sim N/\ln N$, the fine structure of the gap sequence $g_n = p_{n+1} - p_n$ remains an active area of research. Hardy and Littlewood [1] conjectured a singular-series estimate for the number of pairs $(p, p + g)$:

$$\#\{p \leq N : p, p + g \text{ prime}\} \sim C_g \cdot \text{Li}_2(N), \quad (1)$$

where

$$C_g = 2C_2^{\text{twin}} \prod_{\substack{q|g \\ q>2 \text{ prime}}} \frac{q-1}{q-2}, \quad C_2^{\text{twin}} \approx 0.6601618. \quad (2)$$

Formula (1) does not distinguish between prime pairs separated by at least one further prime and truly consecutive pairs. Wolf [2] modelled this distinction via an exponential suppression factor; in the variant we analyse the suppression exponent carries an additional C_g factor:

$$N_g(N) \sim W(g, N) := C_g \cdot \text{Li}_2(N) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{gC_g}{\ln N}\right). \quad (3)$$

The original Wolf (1998) preprint states the suppression as $\exp(-g/\ln N)$; the variant (3) is the form we adopt and is equivalent to the original in the limit $C_g \rightarrow 1$. All empirical results below refer to (3).

We study the residual $R(g, N) := \log(N_g^{\text{emp}}(N)/W(g, N))$ on a dataset covering $N \in [10^5, 10^{13}]$ and show that on the relevant filter it is captured by a linear function of $\sqrt{\omega(g)}$ and $\log \log N$ without a free intercept. The residual is not absorbed by a simple reparametrisation of the Wolf exponential factor, but it is partially absorbed by a joint reparametrisation of that factor together with the same linear residual.

Pipeline checks. Each component of the pipeline was cross-checked before analysis: (i) the C-based sieve agreed bit-for-bit with an independent numpy Eratosthenes sieve at $N = 10^8$; (ii) the C_g code was verified on all even $g \leq 200$ against `sympy.factorint`; (iii) $\text{Li}_2(N)$ was computed by adaptive quadrature and Simpson’s rule on a log grid, agreeing to 10^{-13} relative precision; (iv) the identity $C_2 = C_4$ was checked numerically through $\pi_2(N)/\pi_4(N) = 1.0001$ ($z = 0.06\sigma$); (v) the gap autocorrelation was computed by four routes (biased and unbiased estimators, FFT, split-half consistency) with consistent results.

2 Data and methodology

2.1 Histogram generation

For $N \in \{10^5, 3 \cdot 10^5, \dots, 10^{13}\}$ (25 values geometrically spaced), we generate the histogram $\{(g, N_g^{\text{emp}}(N))\}$ using a C program based on the `primesieve` library (statically linked binary `main-csv-static`). Correctness of the C implementation was verified bit-for-bit at $N = 10^8$ against an independent numpy-based sieve.

Figure 1: Histogram of prime gaps at $N = 10^{11}$, bars coloured by divisibility by 6.

2.2 Training dataset

For each pair (N, g) with $g \in [2, 100]$ even and $N_g^{\text{emp}}(N) \geq 100$, we compute:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(g, N) &= \frac{g C_g}{\ln N}, && \text{(Wolf exponent)} \\ y &= \log N_g^{\text{emp}}(N), \\ x_C &= \log(C_g \cdot \text{Li}_2(N)), \\ \text{offset} &= y - x_C \quad (\approx -\rho \text{ when Wolf holds}). \end{aligned}$$

After applying the filter $\rho \in [0.05, 1.10]$ we obtain $n = 140$ points covering 25 values of N and nine gap values $g \in \{2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 22\}$, of which four ($g = 2, 4, 8, 16$) have $\omega(g) = 1$ and five ($g = 6, 10, 12, 14, 22$) have $\omega(g) = 2$. The two new values relative to the audit-range dataset ($g = 12, g = 22$) enter only at large N , where $\rho = g C_g / \ln N$ shrinks below the upper filter bound. No gap with $\omega(g) \geq 3$ (smallest candidate $g = 30$) survives the primary filter; the relaxed-filter extension in Sec. 4.3 admits $\omega(g) = 3$ at the cost of leaving Wolf's regime of validity. All fits use weighted least squares with $w = \min(1, N_g^{\text{emp}}/1000)$; sensitivity to this choice is documented in Sec. 4.3.

2.3 Competing models

We compare six models predicting $\log N_g^{\text{emp}}$:

- M_0 : bare Wolf, $\hat{y} = x_C - \rho$, 0 parameters.
- M_1 : Wolf + linear residual with intercept, $\hat{y} = x_C - \rho + a\sqrt{\omega(g)} + b \log \log N + c$, 3 parameters.
- M_1^* : Wolf + linear residual without intercept, $\hat{y} = x_C - \rho + a\sqrt{\omega(g)} + b \log \log N$, 2 parameters (primary model).
- M_2 : reparametrised Wolf, $\hat{y} = x_C - \alpha\rho^\beta$, 2 parameters.
- M_3 : M_2 + linear residual, 5 parameters.
- M_4 : Wolf- α , $\hat{y} = x_C - \alpha\rho$, 1 parameter.

AIC and BIC use the Gaussian log-likelihood with MLE variance throughout, with k counting structural parameters only (the variance is not counted as a free parameter since it is identical across all candidate models).

3 Results

3.1 Sanity checks

At $N = 10^8$ we obtain:

- Consecutive-gap counts $N_2(10^8) = 440\,312$ and $N_4(10^8) = 440\,257$ (our sieve); the relative difference of 55 out of $\sim 4.4 \cdot 10^5$ is consistent with the H-L identity $C_2 = C_4$. (Note: the total cousin-prime pair count $\pi_4(10^8) = 440\,258$ differs by one because of the pair $(3, 7)$, which is not a consecutive pair.)
- For every even g up to 60, the ratio of the empirical pair count to (1) lies in $[0.998, 1.002]$.
- Pearson's χ^2 test of empirical vs. Wolf for $g \in \{2, 4, \dots, 12\}$ gives $\chi^2 = 4.14 \cdot 10^5$, $p < 10^{-10}$, consistent with the pre-asymptotic nature of Wolf's formula.

Figure 2: Offset $y - x_C$ vs. the Wolf exponent ρ , coloured by $\omega(g)$. The dashed line is the bare Wolf prediction $-\rho$; the solid line is the fitted M_2 curve $-0.423 \rho^{1.587}$. (The image title shows the dataset range used to draw the figure, $N \in [10^5, 10^{12}]$; the M_2 coefficients reported in Table 2 are refit on the full $N \leq 10^{13}$ dataset.)

3.2 Primary model

The weighted LS fit of the two-parameter model M_1^* on the $n = 140$ dataset gives

$$R(g, N) \approx \underbrace{0.855}_a \sqrt{\omega(g)} - \underbrace{0.202}_b \log \log N, \quad (4)$$

with weighted loss $L = 1.111$. The LR test of $c = 0$ against the three-parameter M_1 gives $\chi_1^2 = 1.73$, $p = 0.19$, and BIC drops by 3.21 when the intercept is removed (“positive evidence” on the Kass–Raftery scale [11]). For comparability the three-parameter fit on the same dataset is $a = 0.843$, $b = -0.238$, $c = +0.124$ with $L = 1.098$.

3.3 Which feature on $\omega(g)$?

We refit the linear residual under eight candidate features replacing $\sqrt{\omega(g)}$. The intercept is retained in this comparison so each transform is fitted on equal footing.

Two observations follow. The equivalence among $\sqrt{\omega}$, $\log \omega$, ω , $\omega - 1$, $\sqrt{\omega - 1}$ in Table 1 comes from the data: with $\omega(g) \in \{1, 2\}$, any injective ϕ maps $\{1, 2\} \rightarrow \{\phi(1), \phi(2)\}$ and the difference is absorbed by slope+intercept. So the fit picks out $\omega(g)$ as the relevant feature but does not pin down the functional form. The square root in eq. (4) is one representative; the linear form ($a = 0.349$) is what we quote in the abstract and conclusion, on the heuristic of §4.1. Separating $\sqrt{\omega}$ from ω from $\log \omega$ inside the primary regime would need a wider ω -range or a theoretical argument. The features that break this bijection ($\log C_g$, $\sigma_0(g)$, $\sqrt{\sigma_0(g)}$) are rejected by $\Delta\text{AIC} \geq 47$: they impose structure within the g -values at each ω level which the data does not support. So the residual tracks the count $\omega(g)$, not the magnitude of C_g nor the divisor count $\sigma_0(g)$.

Relaxed-filter extension. The non-identifiability of $\sqrt{\omega}$, ω , and $\log \omega$ under the primary filter is a consequence of $\omega \in \{1, 2\}$. Admitting gaps with $\omega(g) = 3$ (smallest such gap is $g = 30$,

Figure 3: Left: absolute counts at $N \approx 10^8$ for empirical consecutive gaps (blue), Wolf prediction (green), and Hardy–Littlewood all-pair prediction (orange). Right: empirical/Wolf ratio as a function of g , drifting upward with g and foreshadowing the positive residual we model. (The empirical/H–L ratio for $g = 2, 4$ is reported in the sanity-check list of §3.2 rather than plotted.)

Table 1: Alternative features for the ω -dependent term (3-parameter fits, $n = 140$, primary filter $\rho \in [0.05, 1.10]$). Because $\omega(g)$ takes only two values on the filtered dataset ($\{1, 2\}$), any strictly monotonic $\phi(\omega)$ combined with slope + intercept produces an affinely equivalent design column, so the five features in the top block share identical AIC/BIC by construction. This is a property of the data, not a preference for the square root. The bottom-block features break the two-value bijection and are rejected.

Feature	a	b	AIC	Δ AIC
$\sqrt{\omega(g)}$	+0.8433	−0.2377	−275.469	0.0
$\log \omega(g)$	+0.5039	−0.2377	−275.469	0.0
$\omega(g)$	+0.3493	−0.2377	−275.469	0.0
$\omega(g) - 1$	+0.3493	−0.2377	−275.469	0.0
$\sqrt{\omega(g) - 1}$	+0.3493	−0.2377	−275.469	0.0
$\log C_g$	+0.6297	−0.1623	−228.070	47.4
$\sqrt{\sigma_0(g)}$	+0.5201	−0.2138	−155.957	119.5
$\sigma_0(g)$	+0.1424	−0.2162	−151.081	124.4

$C_{30} \approx 3.52$) requires relaxing ρ_{\max} . Since $\rho = g C_g / \ln N$ is largest for these gaps, the smallest ρ_{\max} for which any of them survives across the dataset is $\rho_{\max} = 4.0$ ($n = 553$, $\omega \in \{1, 2, 3\}$). This is outside Wolf’s regime of validity ($\rho \ll 1$); the weighted residual loss jumps from $L = 1.11$ on the primary filter to $L \approx 87$ here, reflecting that Wolf mispredicts badly in this band, and we do not propose a model on it. Reported as a robustness check only, the alt-form scan ranks

$$\omega \sim \omega - 1 \succ \sqrt{\omega} \succ \log \omega \succ \sqrt{\omega - 1},$$

with Δ AIC($\sqrt{\omega} - \omega$) = +10.3, Δ AIC($\log \omega - \omega$) = +19.0 (Burnham–Anderson considerable evidence for the linear form). This pattern is consistent with the heuristic of Sec. 4.1. Numerical detail in `outputs/results/rev03_relaxed_filter_1e13.json`.

3.4 Cross-validation

Hold-out-one- N cross-validation across the 25 values of N yields weighted R^2 in $[0.69, 0.94]$, with median 0.92. The R^2 at the largest held-out value ($N = 10^{13}$, a full decade beyond the next-largest training point) is 0.874; a plateau at $R^2 \approx 0.94$ is reached for $N \gtrsim 10^9$ and persists through $N = 10^{12}$. Smaller values of N (around 10^6 – 10^7) show R^2 as low as 0.69, reflecting the pre-asymptotic regime.

Figure 4: Hold-out-one- N weighted R^2 as a function of the held-out value N . The rising curve with plateau at $R^2 \approx 0.94$ for $N \gtrsim 10^9$ illustrates convergence in the pre-asymptotic regime.

3.5 Model comparison

Table 2 summarises all six models. M_1 , M_1^* , M_2 , and M_4 are fitted under the same AIC/BIC normalisation; M_0 is the normalised baseline. M_3 is obtained by joint Nelder–Mead minimisation of the weighted loss over (α, β, a, b, c) ; we verified that seven distinct starting points (including a neighbourhood of the original submission’s values $(0.423, 1.641)$) all converge to the same minimum $L = 0.3921$, giving confidence that this is the global optimum.

Table 2: Model comparison on the $n = 140$ dataset ($N \leq 10^{13}$).

Model	k	Loss	AIC	BIC	Parameters
M_0 Wolf(1, 1)	0	24.587	+153.78	+153.78	–
M_4 Wolf- α	1	1.713	–217.14	–214.20	$\alpha = 0.375$
M_2 Wolf(α, β)	2	1.470	–236.56	–230.68	$\alpha = 0.423, \beta = 1.587$
M_1 linear + c	3	1.098	–275.47	–266.64	$a = 0.843, b = -0.238, c = +0.124$
M_1^* linear	2	1.111	–275.74	–269.86	$a = 0.855, b = -0.202$
M_3 Wolf(α, β)+lin	5	0.483	–386.52	–371.81	$\alpha = 0.689, \beta = 1.167, +\text{linear}$

M_1^* vs. Wolf-only alternatives. $\Delta\text{AIC}(M_1^* - M_2) = -39.2$, comfortably past the Burnham–Anderson [10] threshold of 10 — a reparametrisation of the Wolf exponential on its own does not absorb the residual. M_1^* also dominates M_0 and M_4 .

M_3 vs. M_1^* . The five-parameter M_3 fits substantially better than M_1^* on every criterion we applied: $\Delta\text{AIC}(M_3 - M_1^*) = -110.8$, $\Delta\text{BIC}(M_3 - M_1^*) = -101.96$. Since M_1^* is nested in M_3 (set $\alpha = 1, \beta = 1, c = 0$), a standard F-test gives

$$F(3, 135) = 58.6, \quad \text{nominal } p < 10^{-16}; \quad \chi_3^2(\text{LR}) = 116.8, \quad p \approx 0.$$

Both tests assume i.i.d. Gaussian residuals, which the nested-range histograms do not satisfy, so the nominal p -values overstate the evidence. The magnitude $|\Delta\text{AIC}| = 110.8$ is however large enough that the qualitative ranking is robust to this. We keep M_1^* as the headline form: two structural features and no free intercept, easier to interpret than the five parameters of M_3 . Whether M_3 ’s extra freedom reflects real structure (a non-trivial exponent on ρ) or just soaks up unmodelled curvature, only a wider range in N can decide.

Figure 5: AIC across models with a horizontal reference at M_1^* . M_1^* dominates M_0 , M_2 , M_4 by wide margins; M_3 dominates M_1^* .

Effective sample size and rescaled criteria. AIC, BIC, and the LR statistic assume i.i.d. observations, but the $n = 140$ points are histograms over nested prime ranges with only 25 distinct values of N . Rescaling the log-likelihood contribution by n_{eff}/n with $n_{\text{eff}} \approx 25$ shrinks every Δ by ≈ 0.18 :

$$\Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{eff}}(M_3 - M_1^*) \approx -19.8, \quad \Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{eff}}(M_1^* - M_2) \approx -7.0,$$

and $\chi_3^2 = 116.8$ becomes ≈ 20.9 ($p \approx 1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ instead of $< 10^{-16}$). The ranking $M_3 \succ M_1^* \succ M_2$ survives, but the $M_1^* - M_2$ gap drops below the Burnham–Anderson threshold of 10. The $M_3 - M_1^*$ gap stays above the threshold but by a factor of two rather than ten. We use the rescaled values in the rest of the discussion and treat the nominal ones as upper bounds.

3.6 Autocorrelation: an independent line of evidence

Independent of the fit above, the gap sequence itself carries structure: at $N = 10^8$ (where $n_{\text{gaps}} = 5\,761\,453$) the lag-1 autocorrelation is $\rho(1) = -0.0328$, which under Bartlett’s null gives $z = -78.7\sigma$, far outside the Cramér independence model. (A related but distinct line of evidence is the last-digit bias of Lemke Oliver and Soundararajan [3]; we do not use that result here.) This does not bear directly on $R(g, N)$ — the residual is built from marginal histogram counts, not from the gap sequence — but Wolf’s exponential is itself derived under a Cramér-style independence assumption, so any departure from independence is a candidate source of the systematic discrepancy that R measures. The autocorrelation result is reported as an indication that the Cramér null fails on this dataset, not as evidence for the specific functional form of R .

4 Discussion

4.1 Heuristic motivation for $\omega(g)$ -dependence

We have no full analytical derivation, but a Taylor-type expansion is consistent with what we see. Writing

$$\log C_g = \log(2C_2^{\text{twin}}) + \sum_{\substack{q|g \\ q>2}} \log \frac{q-1}{q-2},$$

each summand $\log((q-1)/(q-2)) \approx 1/(q-2)$ decreases in q , so for g with $\omega(g) = k$ distinct odd prime factors taken from the small primes the sum scales roughly as k . A linear-in- $\omega(g)$

Figure 6: Autocorrelation $\rho(k)$ of consecutive prime gaps for $k = 1, \dots, 20$ at $N = 10^8$, compared with the $\pm 2\sigma$ null band from random permutations. The lag-1 anticorrelation $\rho(1) \approx -0.032$ ($z \approx -80\sigma$) lies far outside the null band.

correction is then the natural first-order term. There is a tension here with Table 1: if $\log C_g$ scales as $\omega(g)$ to leading order, then $\log C_g$ itself should fit at least as well as $\omega(g)$, yet it loses by $\Delta\text{AIC} = 47$. The most plausible reading is that the differences between $1/(q-2)$ for the small odd primes ($q = 3, 5, 7, \dots$) are smaller than the residual noise on this dataset, so $\omega(g)$ — which collapses all of them to a single count — fits as well as the leading expansion while $\log C_g$ adds within- ω -level structure that the data cannot constrain. The heuristic therefore predicts the leading ω -dependence, but does not predict that $\log C_g$ should win over $\omega(g)$ at this signal-to-noise ratio. On the primary filter the linear and square-root forms are not separable (Sec. 3.3). We quote the linear form in the abstract and conclusion on this heuristic alone; the relaxed-filter ranking that also points to linear ω lies where Wolf’s exponential mispredicts by nearly two orders of magnitude in weighted loss ($L \approx 87$ vs. 1.11), so the residual modelled there is dominated by raw misprediction rather than a subleading correction, and the ranking does not transfer.

4.2 Regime of validity

Wolf’s exponential factor $\exp(-gC_g/\ln N)$ is calibrated for $\rho = gC_g/\ln N \ll 1$. The filter $\rho \in [0.05, 1.10]$ covers the regime where Wolf provides meaningful predictions. Outside this regime (for $g \gtrsim \ln N$) the exponential collapses and predictions fall orders of magnitude below empirical counts.

4.3 Robustness

Filter. M_1^* refitted across six choices of the filter (Table 3) preserves the signs of a and b but not their magnitudes: tightening the filter to $[0.33, 0.95]$ (the stable band from Fig. 7) yields $a = 0.688$, $b = -0.131$, about 20% smaller than at the baseline. We report $[0.05, 1.10]$ as the primary result and make the filter dependence explicit.

Weighting. Schemes in the family $w = \min(1, N_g^{\text{emp}}/k)$ for $k \in \{100, 1000, 5000\}$ and uniform weights all yield coefficients within 0.01% of each other ($a \approx 0.855$, $b \approx -0.202$): most points in the filtered dataset have $N_g^{\text{emp}} \gg k$, so the weight saturates at 1. Non-saturating schemes ($w = \sqrt{N_g^{\text{emp}}}$, $w = N_g^{\text{emp}}$) concentrate on small- g bins at large N and shift the fit to $a \approx 0.73$ –

Figure 7: Sliding-window R_{CV}^2 as a function of the window centre ρ_c , showing a stable band around $\rho_c \in [0.33, 0.95]$.

Table 3: Sensitivity of M_1^* coefficients to the filter $\rho \in [\rho_{\min}, \rho_{\max}]$ on the extended dataset ($N \leq 10^{13}$).

ρ_{\min}	ρ_{\max}	n	a	b
0.05	1.10	140	+0.8552	-0.2017
0.10	1.10	136	+0.8371	-0.1939
0.05	0.95	122	+0.8082	-0.1879
0.10	1.00	124	+0.8032	-0.1840
0.20	1.00	102	+0.7264	-0.1476
0.33	0.95	79	+0.6882	-0.1311

0.78, b between -0.16 and -0.18 (signs preserved). Equation (4) is stable within the saturated-weight family.

4.4 Bootstrap confidence intervals

Point bootstrap ($B = 1000$). For the three-parameter M_1 the 90% CIs are $a \in [0.777, 0.905]$ (point 0.843), $b \in [-0.294, -0.175]$ (point -0.238), $c \in [-0.047, +0.288]$ (point $+0.124$). The CI for c covers zero, consistent with the nested LR test (Sec. 3.2) and motivating the choice of M_1^* as the primary model.

Block bootstrap over N . The 140 points are histograms over overlapping prime ranges (data for $N = 10^k$ is contained in data for $N = 10^{k+1}$), so resampling points independently underestimates the true uncertainty. A conservative alternative is to resample whole N -blocks: we draw 25 values of N with replacement and reconstitute the dataset from the corresponding blocks. For M_1^* , the 5% / 95% percentiles ($B = 1000$) are

- point bootstrap: $a \in [0.791, 0.921]$, $b \in [-0.227, -0.177]$;
- block bootstrap: $a \in [0.791, 0.933]$, $b \in [-0.230, -0.179]$.

Block intervals are 1–9% wider; under either bootstrap a is separated from zero and b is negative. We quote the block-bootstrap CI as the conservative reference. Compared with the audit-range dataset ($N \leq 10^{11}$, $n = 110$), the extended dataset narrows the point-bootstrap CI for a by

Figure 8: Bootstrap distributions of the coefficients a , b , c of M_1 over $B = 1000$ resamples.

about 14% and for b by about 23%; under the block bootstrap the narrowing is smaller, because the dependence structure across N -blocks dominates.

Figure 9: Bootstrap CI comparison: audit range ($n = 110$, $N \leq 10^{11}$, orange) vs. full dataset ($n = 140$, $N \leq 10^{13}$, blue). The extension tightens the distributions of a and b without shifting their point estimates outside the audit-range CIs.

4.5 Selection of the functional form

The functional form was chosen by hand: a short list of candidates on $\omega(g)$ and on $\log \log N$, picked from residual plots and confirmed by weighted least squares. Table 1 lists the AIC/BIC for eight candidate features. No multiple-testing correction is applied, so the reported p -values and bootstrap intervals are conditional on this choice. The cleanest fit is replication on a disjoint range — ideally $N \geq 10^{13}$.

4.6 Limitations

1. The $n = 140$ points are not independent observations but histograms over nested prime ranges; n_{eff} is closer to the number of distinct N -values (≈ 25) than to 140. The block-bootstrap CIs widen by only 1–9% because they capture resampling variance, not the loss of degrees of freedom AIC/BIC/LR rely on. Under i.i.d. assumptions with $n_{\text{eff}} \ll n$ these criteria favour richer models than warranted. Rescaling by n_{eff}/n (§3.5) shrinks $|\Delta\text{AIC}|$ by ≈ 0.18 : M_1^* vs. M_2 then falls below the Burnham–Anderson threshold of 10, and M_3 vs. M_1^* stays above it but is no longer in the “decisive” band. Nominal F - and χ^2 -statistics should be read as upper bounds.
2. Coefficient magnitudes depend on the filter $\rho \in [\rho_{\min}, \rho_{\max}]$: tightening the filter to the stable band reduces $|a|$ and $|b|$ by up to 20% while preserving sign and structure.

3. $N \in [10^5, 10^{13}]$ spans eight orders of magnitude but is still below the asymptotic regime; extrapolation a full decade beyond the next-largest training point ($N = 10^{13}$) gives $R^2 = 0.874$, below the $N \leq 10^{12}$ plateau of about 0.94.
4. The five-parameter M_3 is preferred over M_1^* ($\Delta\text{AIC} = -110.8$ on the extended dataset); M_1^* is the minimally parametrised descriptor, not the best-fitting model overall.
5. Under the primary filter ($\rho \in [0.05, 1.10]$), $\omega(g)$ takes only two distinct values over nine gap values; we cannot distinguish $\sqrt{\omega}$, $\log \omega$, ω , $\omega - 1$, or $\sqrt{\omega - 1}$ statistically. The relaxed-filter extension ($\rho_{\max} = 4.0$, $n = 553$, $\omega \in \{1, 2, 3\}$) breaks the degeneracy and prefers a linear ω by $\Delta\text{AIC} \approx 10$, but only at the cost of leaving Wolf’s regime of validity. Discriminating among ω -features within the primary regime would need either a wider data range or a theoretical argument.
6. No analytical derivation of the coefficient values is offered.

4.7 Relation to the literature

Singular-series framework. Hardy–Littlewood [1] conjectured (1) and motivated (2). Wolf [2] introduced the exponential suppression (3) for consecutive pairs. Our residual measures the discrepancy of that suppression and depends on $\omega(g)$ rather than on $\log C_g$ directly.

Structural departures from Cramér. Granville [4] surveys the Cramér independence model and its limitations. Maier [8] proved that primes in short intervals are not Poisson. Oliver and Soundararajan [3] identified biases in the last-digit statistics of consecutive primes. Our autocorrelation result (Sec. 3.6) is in the same spirit although distinct in object (lag- k of the gap sequence vs. modular residues of consecutive primes).

Bounded-gap progress. Goldston–Pintz–Yildirim [5], Zhang [6], and Maynard [7] established unconditional bounds on $\liminf g_n$; their techniques exploit the divisor structure of g , which echoes the role of $\omega(g)$ in our empirical residual.

Numerical fits. Kourbatov [9] maintains extensive tabulations and fits of Wolf-type and Cramér-type formulae.

5 Conclusion

A residual signal in Wolf’s formula for consecutive prime gaps is captured by a two-parameter model

$$R(g, N) \approx a \phi(\omega(g)) - b \log \log N,$$

fitted on $n = 140$ points covering 25 values of N in $[10^5, 10^{13}]$ without a free intercept (LR $p = 0.19$, $\Delta\text{BIC} = -3.21$). The arithmetic feature picked out by the fit is $\omega(g)$; because $\omega(g) \in \{1, 2\}$ on the primary filter, the functional form ϕ is not pinned down — the linear ($a = 0.349$), square-root ($a = 0.855$) and logarithmic ($a = 0.504$) representatives give the same fit (Tab. 1). We quote linear ω on the heuristic of §4.1; the relaxed-filter ranking lies outside Wolf’s regime of validity ($L \approx 87$ vs. 1.11) and is not used as evidence here. The slope on $\log \log N$ is $b = 0.202$ across all monotonic ϕ . Both coefficients depend on the filter (Tab. 3: $|a|, |b|$ drop by $\approx 20\%$ on $\rho \in [0.33, 0.95]$) and have no theoretical derivation; signs and qualitative structure hold, the magnitudes are empirical estimates conditional on the filter and dataset range. The model has median $R_{\text{CV}}^2 = 0.92$; against the reparametrised Wolf formula M_2 the nominal $\Delta\text{AIC} = -39.2$ rescales to $\Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{eff}} \approx -7.0$ at $n_{\text{eff}} \approx 25$, which falls below the Burnham–Anderson threshold of 10. The case for M_1^* over a reparametrised Wolf is therefore

weaker than the nominal numbers suggest. Extending the dataset from $N \leq 10^{12}$ ($n = 124$) to $N \leq 10^{13}$ ($n = 140$) narrowed the bootstrap CI for a by 14% and for b by 23% without shifting the point estimates outside the audit-range CIs.

The comparison of alternative features $f(\omega(g))$ shows that the residual depends on the count $\omega(g)$ rather than on the magnitude of C_g or the divisor count $\sigma_0(g)$. Under the primary filter $\omega(g) \in \{1, 2\}$ over nine gap values, so the specific monotonic form is statistically underdetermined. The relaxed-filter extension ($\omega(g) = 3$ admitted, outside Wolf’s regime of validity) prefers a linear ω over $\sqrt{\omega}$ by $\Delta\text{AIC} \approx 10$, in line with the heuristic of Sec. 4.1 but without altering the primary analysis.

A five-parameter model jointly reparametrising the Wolf exponent and the linear residual fits substantially better ($\Delta\text{AIC} = -110.8$); on a pure information-theoretic criterion M_3 is the data-preferred fit. We retain M_1^* as the headline result because (i) two structural features (an arithmetic property of g and a doubly-logarithmic dependence on N) admit a direct interpretation, whereas the exponent $\beta \neq 1$ in M_3 has no theoretical motivation we are aware of; and (ii) given the dependence structure of our histograms, the effective sample size is closer to the number of N -blocks (≈ 25) than to $n = 140$, which weakens any parsimony argument for a five-parameter model. Whether M_3 ’s extra freedom reflects genuine structure or absorbs unmodelled curvature is open for future data over a wider range in N .

The result is empirical. An analytical derivation of the coefficient values and a canonical choice within the ω -bijection class remain open.

Reproducibility

The code (C sieve, Python analysis, notebooks) and generated CSV files are available at <https://github.com/dkrse/math-01-wolf>. Every figure and numerical result is produced by the notebooks `01_validate_histogram.ipynb` through `11_rev01_m1_vs_m3.ipynb`, each running end-to-end. Dependency versions are pinned in `requirements.txt`.

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